

Gross Profit Margin (GPM) in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Gross Profit Margin (GPM) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and literature review. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the GPM ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the GPM ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the GPM ratio using a literature review study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 79 journal publications regarding the GPM ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the GPM ratio are divided into 7 clusters and 131 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of literature review studies, there are 19 topics around the influence of the GPM ratio and 10 topics about the determinants of the GPM ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around GPM ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Gross Profit Margin (GPM), Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Banking

INTRODUCTION

The development of the use of the Gross Profit Margin (GPM) ratio in banking can be seen as a response to the development of an increasingly complex and competitive financial industry. Along with the development of financial technology (fintech), banks are now faced with increasingly fierce competition from competitors who are more innovative and efficient. In situations like these, the GPM ratio can be a very useful tool for companies to measure progress in improving their business efficiency. In its use, the GPM ratio is calculated by dividing gross income by total income. This ratio provides an idea of how large a percentage of income is obtained from effective operational activities. The higher the GPM ratio, the better the company's performance in generating gross income from its operational activities.

Apart from that, the GPM ratio can also be used to compare efficiency between different banks. In the growing banking industry, performance comparisons between companies are very important for investors, customers and regulators. The GPM ratio can help these parties to compare banking performance more accurately and objectively. Lastly, the GPM ratio can also be used to evaluate overall business performance. In an increasingly dynamic business environment, companies need to evaluate their business performance regularly to ensure that they remain effective and efficient in generating revenue. By using the GPM ratio, companies can get a clear picture of how effective they are in generating gross income from their operational activities. In conclusion, the use of the GPM ratio in banking is a very important tool for measuring a company's efficiency in generating gross income from its operational activities. In an increasingly complex and competitive financial industry environment, the GPM ratio can be a very useful tool for companies to increase their business efficiency and ensure optimal business performance.

Research on GPM in banking has been carried out in recent years. This research aims to measure and evaluate the efficiency and performance of the banking business in generating gross income from its operational activities. First, several studies have shown that the GPM ratio is one of the most important performance indicators for banks. This research shows that the GPM ratio

can be used to measure banking efficiency in generating gross income, and can also be used to compare performance between different banks. Second, research also shows that the GPM ratio can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of business strategies and banking operational policies. In an increasingly dynamic and complex business environment, banks need to continuously evaluate and adjust their business strategies and operational policies so that they remain effective and efficient in generating income. Third, research also shows that the use of the GPM ratio in banking can help investors and regulators to understand banking business performance better. The GPM ratio can provide a clear picture of how effective banks are in generating gross income from their operational activities, so that it can help investors and regulators to make more appropriate investment and supervisory decisions. Fourth, research also shows that the use of the GPM ratio in banking can help companies identify and deal with business efficiency problems. By monitoring the GPM ratio regularly, companies can identify business areas that are less effective and take the necessary actions to improve business efficiency and performance. In conclusion, the development of research on Gross Profit Margin (GPM) in banking shows that this ratio is one of the most important performance indicators for banks. By using the GPM ratio, banks can measure their business efficiency and performance, as well as identify business problems and opportunities that can help them to improve business efficiency and performance.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around GPM in Sharia and Conventional Banking using: (1) VOSviewer bibliometric studies to analyze and study maps of literature developments in publications in a scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) literature study review to analyze, identify and review articles from the accredited national journal Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding GPM. This can be a reference for other researchers who wish to research GPM. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics around the GPM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that they can become a reference for subsequent researchers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gross Profit Margin (GPM) is a financial ratio that measures how effectively a company earns revenue from sales of their products or services after deducting the direct costs of producing or procuring goods. However, in banking, GPM has a slightly different meaning. In banking, GPM measures how effective banks are in generating revenue from the products and services they offer after deducting direct costs such as interest paid to customers and operational costs. In this case, direct banking costs include deposit interest, loan interest, and costs related to services such as administration fees and transaction fees. In general, the higher a bank's GPM, the more efficient it is at generating revenue from their products and services. However, it should be remembered that GPM does not provide a complete picture of a bank's financial performance and should be viewed together with other financial ratios to obtain a more comprehensive picture of the bank's financial health.

Bibliometric studies are studies that use quantitative methods to analyze and understand scientific publications and existing literature in a particular field or topic. Bibliometric methods are used to analyze and measure the quantity and quality of scientific literature that has been published in journals or books, such as the number of articles, authors, citations, and frequency of citations. In bibliometric studies, bibliographic data is used to identify research trends and patterns in a particular field, such as concept development, important issues, or the impact of research works on the development of science. Bibliometric studies can assist researchers in conducting systematic literature analyzes and provide empirical evidence to support conclusions or hypotheses in their research. Bibliometric studies can also assist publishers, journal editors, and libraries in understanding reader preferences, identifying topics of greatest interest, and monitoring research trends. As a research method, bibliometric studies can provide better insight and understanding of how research develops over time, and help guide the direction of future research.

VOSviewer is data analysis software used for visualization of bibliometric data. This software is designed to assist researchers and professionals in understanding and analyzing research performance in a particular field based on bibliographic data. In VOSviewer, bibliographic data is presented in network form, where each element in the network represents an article or document. This network can be presented in the form of graphs and diagrams to facilitate understanding and analysis. VOSviewer can be used to identify relationships between articles or authors in a particular research field, as well as assist in understanding research trends and research focus. This software can also help in conducting citation analysis, co-citation analysis, and other bibliometric analysis. VOSviewer can be used with various types of bibliographic data, such as data from scientific publication databases, citation databases, or other bibliometric data sources. This software is a useful tool for researchers and professionals in various research fields, including social sciences, computer science, and natural sciences, and can be used as an aid in decision making and research strategy.

Studies literature review is a form of research carried out by analyzing and evaluating existing literature in a particular field. In a literature review, researchers search for literature related to their research topic and analyze the data found. The purpose of a literature review study is to provide a comprehensive picture of existing knowledge in a particular field, and help identify research gaps that need to be filled in that field. Literature reviews can also assist researchers in building a theoretical framework for their research and validating the methodology used. In a literature review, researchers must go through a series of systematic stages, including planning a literature search, selecting inclusion and exclusion criteria, evaluating the quality of the literature, and data synthesis. Ultimately, researchers should be able to produce a clear and structured report that summarizes their findings in the literature review. Literature review studies can be conducted in various research fields, including social sciences, natural sciences, health, and information technology. Literature reviews are a useful tool for researchers in providing a detailed knowledge base about their research topic, and assisting in the development of more effective and informed research.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is Gross Profit Margin (GPM). The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on GPM in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

The source of data collection comes from search for accredited national journals, Sinta via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keywords " Gross Profit Margin " and " GPM " over the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding GPM using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based on publication year; (2) mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around GPM using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around GPM using a literature review study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Journal Publications Regarding Gross Profit Margin (GPM) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

There are 79 national journals accredited by Sinta based on the results of data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop originating from the Garuda website (Digital

Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software during the period 2007 to 2022. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about GPM by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2007	1	2016	1	2020	15
2009	1	2017	2	2021	15
2011	1	2018	6	2022	24
2015	2	2019	11		

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Mapping Regarding Gross Profit Margin (GPM) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around GPM. Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer related to the research development map regarding the GPM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, there are 7 clusters and 131 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, consists of 29 topic items, namely: annual report, assets, bank, equity, financial performance, financial ratio/statement, form, formulation, gpm, investment, investor, level, net profit margin, npm, opm, influence of returns, performance, company, problem, profit, profit margin, profitability ratio, quick ratio, ratio, return, roa, roe, share price.
- Cluster 2, consists of 21 topic items, namely: analysis technique, asset ratio, bei, dar, effect, financial distress, independent variable, Indonesian stock exchange, manufacturing company, multiple linear regression, multiple regression analysis,

negative effect, influence of gross profit margin, population, purposive sampling method, quantitative approach, relationship secondary data, tattoo, value.

- Cluster 3, consists of 21 topic items, namely: current ratio, debt, der, Indonesian effect, equity ratio, table, gross profit margin, Indonesia, inventory turnover, method, working capital, influence of current ratio, influence of debt, regression testing, company, receivable turnover, significant to gross profit margin, spss, hypothesis test, t test.
- Cluster 4, consists of 19 topic items, namely: autocorrelation, classic assumption test, company, criteria, data analysis technique, earnings growth, f test, financial report, food, income, influence, inventory value, market value, multicollinearity, profit growth, sampling method, significant influence, total assets.
- Cluster 5, consists of 15 topic items, namely: analytical method, classical assumption test, coefficient, determination, difference, growth, hypothesis testing, nippin indosari corpinda, purposive sampling technique, quantitative method, sales growth, spss version, t test, tbk type.
- Cluster 6, consists of 15 topic items, namely: contribution, covid, current ratio and total assets, data analysis, data collection technique, fcount, ftable, idx, pandemic, purposive sampling, sampling technique, significance, significant effect, tcount, total asset turnover.
- cluster 7, consists of 11 topic items, namely: Indonesian stock exchange, dividend payout ratio, earnings per share, EPS, stock price, index, multiple linear regression, positive effect, share, stock price.

Mapping Literature Review Study regarding the Influence of Gross Profit Margin (GPM) on Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 19 influences of GPM on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, benchmarking tax aggressiveness. The influence of GPM on benchmarking tax aggressiveness in banking will depend on the tax policy adopted by the company. If a company has a high GPM, it means that the company is more efficient in carrying out its operations and is able to generate quite large revenues. In this case, the company may be better able to pay higher amounts of tax, and have more conservative tax policies than its competitors. Conversely, if a company has a low GPM, it may be more aggressive in pursuing cost reductions and paying lower taxes.

Second, Earning Per Share/EPS. The effect of GPM on EPS in banking will depend on various other factors such as operational costs, interest and tax burden, and investment performance. If a company is able to generate income that is higher than its operating costs, then its EPS is likely to increase. However, if operating costs increase faster than revenue, then EPS will likely decline.

Third, Financial distress in Technology. GPM can affect financial distress in technology companies in banking, in several ways: (1) Low GPM can indicate operational efficiency problems or unprofitable sales, thereby reducing the profits obtained by the company. This can cause financial difficulties and the risk of financial distress. (2) High GPM can help a company generate sufficient profits to meet its financial obligations and have sufficient cash reserves to face future risks and uncertainties. This can help reduce the risk of financial distress. (3) Stable and consistent GPM can help a company build a good reputation in the eyes of investors and creditors, and provide confidence that the company can fulfill its financial obligations. This can help reduce the risk of financial distress.

Fourth, share prices. The influence of GPM on share prices in banks can vary depending on other factors that influence the bank's financial performance. In general, an increase in GPM is usually considered a positive indication of a bank's financial performance and can trigger an increase in share prices. However, other factors such as credit risk, income growth, and macroeconomic factors can also influence banking share prices.

Fifth, income smoothing. When banking GPM increases, companies may tend to smooth profits by delaying the recognition of some expenses or increasing revenue estimates. This is done to maintain consistent profits in the company's financial reports, especially if business performance does not show significant growth. However, if GPM decreases, a company may be inclined to increase expenses or lower revenue estimates to avoid a significant decline in profits. In this context, the practice of income smoothing can be carried out to influence investors' and financial analysts' perceptions of company performance. However, this practice can also pose significant accounting risks and negatively impact the trust of a company's stakeholders. Therefore, companies need to carefully consider their decisions in income smoothing and ensure that their financial reports comply with applicable accounting standards.

Sixth, economic indicators. The influence of GPM on economic indicators depends on the industry and market in question. In general, the higher the GPM, the better a company's financial performance, which can reflect stronger economic conditions. Apart from that, GPM can also provide clues about a company's market strength and the company's ability to compete with competitors in the market.

Seventh, dividend policy. Dividend policy in banking can also be influenced by GPM. If GPM increases, then the company can have more profits to distribute to shareholders in the form of dividends. However, dividend policy is also influenced by other factors such as company growth, management policies, and market conditions. For example, if banks decide to allocate more profits for business growth, then dividend policy may not be so aggressive even though GPM increases.

Eighth, the decision to carry out transfer pricing. GPM can influence the decision to carry out transfer pricing because GPM reflects the level of profit obtained from the products and services offered by the company. If the company's GPM is low, then the company may tend to carry out transfer pricing to move profits from business units that generate higher profits to business units that generate lower profits. However, carrying out transfer pricing with the aim of avoiding taxes or breaking the law can have a negative impact on the company's image and trigger legal action that is detrimental to the company. Therefore, companies need to consider the long-term benefits and risks of transfer pricing before making this decision.

Ninth, financial performance. The influence of GPM on banking financial performance can be seen from several points of view: (1) Profitability: high GPM indicates good profitability. The higher the GPM, the greater the gross profit generated by the company. In this case, banks can increase their profitability by increasing GPM through strategies such as increasing credit interest rates or reducing interest costs. (2) Efficiency: Low GPM may indicate poor efficiency in productive asset management. Therefore, banks can increase their efficiency by increasing GPM through better management of productive assets, such as by increasing more optimal credit distribution or reducing high interest costs. (3) Risk: A high GPM can indicate low risk, because the bank has more profit margin that can be used to cover credit risk or market risk. However, keep in mind that a high GPM can also indicate that the bank is taking too little risk, thereby not maximizing potential profits. (4) Growth: Stable and good GPM can provide support for banking growth, because banks have more profit margins that can be used to expand business or develop new products.

Tenth, the company's market value. The influence of GPM on Market Value in banking can vary depending on various factors, such as the banking sector, economic conditions, and internal factors of the company itself. However, in general, companies with higher GPM tend to have higher Market Value too. This is due to the fact that a higher GPM indicates that the company is able to generate greater gross profit than revenue, which in turn can indicate higher operational efficiency. This can result in increased investor confidence and increase demand for the company's shares in the market, which can increase the company's market value. However, a high GPM value alone is not enough to guarantee a high market value. There are many other factors that can influence market value, such as a company's overall financial performance, profit growth, and the overall health of the economy. Therefore, it is important for companies to consider these various factors when trying to increase their market value.

Eleventh, Net Profit Margin/NPM. GPM has an influence on NPM in banking. The higher the GPM of a bank, the greater the possibility that the bank will have a higher NPM. This is because the higher the GPM, the more money available to cover the bank's operational costs and generate net profits.

Twelfth, company value. In the banking context, GPM may not have a direct influence on company value. This is because in the banking industry, factors such as credit performance, asset growth, and net cash flow may be more important in determining a company's value than more specific financial ratios such as GPM. However, the higher a bank's GPM, the more money it has available to cover operational costs and invest in business growth. This can lead to greater revenue and profit growth, which in turn can increase the company's value on the stock market.

Thirteenth, market value. In the banking industry, GPM may not have a significant direct influence on the market value of a bank. However, a high GPM can be an indicator to investors that the bank is capable of generating large profits from its core business, which can increase investor confidence in the bank's future prospects. On the other hand, a low GPM can be a warning sign to investors that the bank may be having difficulty generating profits, and this can affect the bank's market value.

Fourteenth, profit growth. The influence of GPM on profit growth in banking is very important. As banking, banking generates income from interest and fees charged on financial products. Banking GPM can be influenced by many factors, such as interest rates, competition, operational costs and credit risk. When banking GPM increases, it means that the gross profit generated from sales of financial products increases. This can increase the growth of banking net profits, because gross profits can be used to pay operational costs and strengthen banking capital. In the long term, high GPM can also attract investors to invest in banking, which in the end can increase company value and profit growth.

Fifteenth, disclosure of Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR. Several studies indicate that companies with high GPM tend to be more active in disclosing CSR compared to companies with low GPM. This is because companies with high GPM have greater financial resources and the ability to finance social activities. Apart from that, CSR disclosure can also help companies improve the company's image and reputation in the eyes of customers and the wider community, which can ultimately improve the company's financial performance.

Sixteenth, Return On Assets/ROA. GPM can influence ROA in banking because GPM indicates how efficient a company is in managing costs and gaining profits from selling products or services. The higher the GPM of a company, the greater the gross profit the company generates from each sale, which in turn can increase the company's ROA. In other words, companies with high GPM can take advantage of greater gross profits to increase net profits and ROA.

Seventeenth, Return On Equity/ROE. GPM can influence ROE in banking because GPM indicates how efficient a company is in managing costs and making profits from selling products or services. The higher the GPM of a company, the greater the gross profit the company generates from each sale, which ultimately can increase the company's net profit and ROE. In other words, companies with high GPM can take advantage of greater gross profits to increase ROE.

Eighteenth, Return On Investment/ROI. GPM can influence ROI in banking because GPM indicates how efficient a company is in managing costs and gaining profits from selling products or services. The higher the GPM of a company, the greater the gross profit the company generates from each sale, which can ultimately increase the company's net profit and ROI. In other words, companies with high GPM can leverage greater gross profits to increase ROI.

Nineteenth, stock returns. GPM can influence stock returns in banking because GPM shows how efficient the company is in managing costs and making profits from selling products or services. The higher the company's GPM, the greater the profits the company can obtain and the greater the possibility of the company providing larger dividends to shareholders, thereby increasing stock returns.

Mapping the Literature Review Study regarding the Determinant Variables of Gross Profit Margin (GPM) in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Literature review study in previous research journals, researchers found 10 determinant variables of GPM in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, Covid-19. However, in general, Covid-19 can affect GPM in banking in several ways: (1) Decrease in Revenue: Covid-19 causes a decline in revenue in many economic sectors, including the banking industry. This decrease could reduce banking GPM because gross profit will decrease due to a decrease in revenue. (2) Additional operational costs: Covid-19 may force banks to incur additional costs to face the challenges of the pandemic, such as costs for disseminating information about banking services available during the pandemic, health equipment and cleaning supplies for employees and customers, as well as costs for ensuring availability sufficient cash at ATMs and branches. This additional fee can reduce banking GPM. (3) Increased bad debts: Covid-19 has affected many businesses and individuals, and could impact their ability to repay debts. If bad loans increase, banks must record losses for reserves created to handle bad loans, which can reduce GPM. (4) Lowering interest rates: In an effort to stimulate economic growth, central banks may lower interest rates. This decline could affect banking GPM because their net interest margin decreases. (5) Increase in digital transactions: Covid-19 forced many consumers to switch to digital transactions due to social restrictions and lockdowns. This increase in digital transactions can increase banking GPM because digital transactions are usually more efficient and have lower costs than physical transactions.

Second, Current Ratio. Current Ratio can influence GPM in banking in several ways: (1) Liquidity: Current Ratio shows the bank's ability to pay short-term obligations with current assets. If Current A high ratio means that banks have good liquidity, and this can enable banks to minimize loan costs and increase their GPM. (2) Operational Efficiency: Current Ratio can also influence banking operational efficiency. If the Current Ratio is low, it means that banks have limited liquidity, and may have to borrow funds to meet their operational needs. This can increase borrowing costs and reduce GPM. (4) Bad Credit Rate: If banks have a low Current Ratio, they may be more susceptible to credit risk and bad debts. Bad credit can affect GPM because banks have to create reserves to handle credit risk, which can reduce gross profit and GPM. (5) Interest Rates: Interest rates can affect the Current Ratio and GPM in banking. If interest rates increase, banks may need to pay more loan fees, and this may affect the Current Ratio and GPM. Conversely, if interest rates fall, banks may be able to pay less loan costs, increase the Current Ratio, and increase GPM.

Third, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER. DER can influence GPM in banking in several ways: (1) Financial Risk: DER can influence banking financial risk because the higher the DER, the greater the financial risk that banks must face. Financial risk can affect GPM because banks have to establish reserves to handle financial risks, which can reduce gross profit and GPM. (2) Loan Costs: DER can also affect bank loan costs. If DER is high, banks may need to pay higher interest on their debt, which can reduce gross profit and GPM. Conversely, if DER is low, banks may be able to pay lower interest on their debt, which can increase GPM. (3) Capital Structure: DER can influence banks' capital structure and their funding sources. If the DER is high, it means that banks use more debt to fund their operations. This can increase financial risks and borrowing costs. However, if DER is low, banks may rely more on their own capital to fund their operations, which can increase financial stability and GPM. (4) Operational Efficiency: DER can affect banking operational efficiency because banks have to pay interest on their debts. If DER is high, interest costs can reduce gross profit and GPM. However, if banks can manage their debt well and pay reasonable interest, then DER can provide additional funding that allows banks to increase operational efficiency and GPM.

Fourth, Inventory Turnover/IT. In the banking context, because banks do not sell inventory, IT does not have a direct influence on GPM. However, there are several ways in which IT can influence GPM indirectly: (1) Credit: Banks provide credit to their customers, thereby requiring capital supplies to accommodate credit demand. The faster banks can distribute credit, the less capital is needed to handle the demand. Thus, high IT can enable banks to minimize the capital required and obtain higher profits. (2) Operational: The higher the IT, the lower the capital stock required to carry out banking operations. This can improve operational efficiency and help

increase GPM. (3) Risk management: IT can also affect banking operational risks, as banks must manage risks related to their capital stock. The higher the IT, the less capital stock has to be handled, which can reduce operational risks and enable banks to earn higher profits.

Fifth, leverage. In the banking context, leverage can significantly influence GPM. The following are some of the effects of leverage on GPM in banking: (1) Interest costs: The higher the leverage, the more debt the bank must pay as interest. High interest costs can reduce GPM because these costs reduce the profits generated by banks. (2) Credit risk: The higher the leverage, the greater the credit risk that banks must handle. If a payment default or bad credit occurs, banks will have to bear greater losses, which can reduce GPM. (3) Capital resilience: The higher the leverage, the less capital is available to respond to banking risks and financial needs. In difficult market conditions, highly leveraged banks may face difficulties maintaining capital adequacy, which may impact GPM.

Sixth, quantitative and qualitative working capital. Working capital is the amount of current assets available to a company to carry out daily operations. Working capital consists of current assets such as cash, inventory, accounts receivable, and short-term investments minus current liabilities such as accounts payable and accrued expenses. There are two types of working capital, namely quantitative and qualitative working capital. Quantitative working capital is the amount of money available for use by a company in carrying out daily operations. Qualitative working capital is a company's ability to manage assets and liabilities effectively and efficiently. Gross Profit Margin (GPM) is a ratio that measures the efficiency of a company's operating costs in generating gross profits. Quantitative working capital can affect GPM because the company must have sufficient working capital to finance daily operations. If companies do not have sufficient working capital, they may have difficulty meeting obligations and paying operational costs, which can lower GPM. However, too much working capital can also reduce GPM because the company has to pay interest on the money borrowed to finance working capital. Meanwhile, qualitative working capital can influence GPM because companies must be able to manage assets and liabilities effectively and efficiently. If companies cannot manage their inventory well, they may experience losses due to expired or damaged inventory. If companies cannot manage their receivables well, they may experience losses because receivables cannot be collected properly. If companies cannot manage their obligations well, they may have difficulty paying accounts payable or paying accrued expenses. Therefore, quantitative and qualitative working capital can influence GPM in banking. To maximize GPM, banks must ensure that they have sufficient working capital to finance daily operations and can also manage assets and liabilities effectively and efficiently. In this way, banks can earn higher profits and increase the efficiency of their operating costs.

Seventh, cash turnover. Cash turnover can influence GPM in banking because good cash management can help companies save costs and increase profits. When companies can manage their cash well, they can earn higher interest on their investments and minimize borrowing costs. In the banking context, high cash turnover can indicate that banks are able to manage cash well and use it to finance their operations. In other words, banks can generate higher profits with lower costs, which can increase their GPM. However, cash turnover that is too high can also indicate that the company is too conservative in taking risks or not focused enough on growth. Conversely, cash turnover that is too low can indicate that the company is too aggressive in taking risks or less effective in managing their cash. These two conditions can affect GPM in banking in different ways. Therefore, to maximize GPM, banks must ensure that they have a balanced cash turnover, i.e. high enough to demonstrate efficiency in cash management, but also low enough to demonstrate a focus on growth and healthy risk taking. In this way, banks can increase the efficiency of their operating costs and maximize their profits.

Eighth, receivables turnover. Receivables turnover can also affect Gross Profit Margin (GPM) in banking. This is because higher receivable turnover can result in a decrease in GPM in banking. This happens because companies have to give discounts or reduce selling prices to customers who pay quickly, thereby reducing the profit margin obtained. In addition, if a company accelerates receivables turnover by reducing the quality of credit provided to customers, this can

increase credit risk and reduce the quality of the company's assets. On the other hand, if a company slows down its receivables turnover, this can increase GPM because the company can maintain a higher profit margin. In the banking context, the effect of receivables turnover on GPM must be considered in relation to the balance between credit risk and profitability. Therefore, companies must pay attention to optimal receivables turnover which can help increase cash flow and profitability without increasing unnecessary credit risk.

Ninth, Receivable Turnover. In banking, the influence of Receivable Turnover on Gross Profit Margin/GPM may not be very significant because banks do not rely on receivables from customers as their main source of income. In contrast, banks generate income from interest and fees charged on the services and products they offer. However, banks still need sufficient liquidity to run their business operations well. High receivable turnover can help banks optimize cash flow and minimize the risk of uncollectible credit, thereby helping to increase the overall efficiency of banking operations. In addition, if banks issue credit to their customers, low receivable turnover can indicate that the company has difficulty collecting payments from their customers, which can increase the risk of uncollectible credit and can affect banking GPM. Overall, Receivable Turnover can influence GPM in banking in an indirect way, by helping to increase operational efficiency and reduce the risk of uncollectible credit. However, this role may not be as big as in other companies that rely on receivables from customers as their main source of income.

Tenth, Total Asset Turnover/TATO. In the banking industry, TATO can influence GPM because banking assets are mainly in the form of loans and investments that generate interest income and fees charged to customers. The higher the TATO, the more efficient the company is in utilizing its assets to generate income and therefore can increase GPM. However, the effect of TATO on GPM is not always linear. In some cases, an increase in TATO may lead to a decrease in GPM if the company chooses to reduce loan interest rates or increase the cost of raising funds. Conversely, a decrease in TATO can increase GPM if the company chooses to optimize loan quality by reducing credit risk.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: first, based on the mapping of the distribution of journal publications regarding Gross Profit Margin (GPM) ratios in Sharia and Conventional Banking during the period 2007 to 2022 originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 79 published journal articles. Second, based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results regarding the GPM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking are divided into 7 clusters and 131 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 29 topics, cluster 2 consists of 21 topics, cluster 3 consists of 21 topics, cluster 4 consists of 19 topics, cluster 5 consists of 15 topics, cluster 6 consists of 15 topics, and cluster 7 consists of 11 topics.. Third, based on mapping studies literature review, there are 19 topics related to the influence of the GPM ratio on Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Benchmarking tax aggressiveness, Earning Per Share/EPS, Financial distress in Technology, share prices, income smoothing/profit smoothing, economic indicators, dividend policy, decision to carry out praicing transfers, financial performance, company market value, Net Profit Margin/NPM, company value, market value, profit growth, Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR disclosure, Return On Assets/ROA, Return On Equity/ROE, Return On Investment/ROI, and return share. And there are 10 topics related to the determinants of the GPM ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely: Covid-19, Current Ratio, Debt to Equity Ratio/DER, Inventory Turnover/IT, leverage, quantitative and qualitative working capital, cash turnover, receivables turnover, Receivable Turnover, and Total Asset Turnover/TATO.

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